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PRELIMINARY RESEARCH ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF A TECHNOLOGY FOR PRODUCING AMORPHOUS SILICA BASED ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents preliminary research on the production of amorphous silica based on local raw materials. In the study, the main object selected was the rock formations of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite deposit, located in the Sultan Uvays mountain range in the Lower Amudarya region of our Republic, with total reserves of 23 468,7 thousand tons. Based on the identified chemical composition of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite, the theoretical stages of obtaining amorphous silica from this raw material are described. According to the study, the extraction of amorphous silica from these rocks mainly consists of thermal processing of the raw material at 900–1200 °C, followed by dissolution in an alkaline solution to form alkaline silicate, and subsequent acid treatment of the obtained product.

Keywords: *Amorphous silica (SiO₂), talc, talk-magnesit, Zinelbulak talc-magnesite, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), infrared (IR) spectroscopy.*

AMORF KREMNEZEM OLI SHNING MAHALLIY XOM ASHYOLARGA ASOSLANGAN TEXNOLOGIYASINI YARATISH BORASIDAGI DASTLABKI TADQIQOTLAR

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada mahalliy xom ashyolar asosida amorf kremnezem olish borasida olib borilayotgan dastlabki tadqiqotlar haqida bayon qilingan. Tadqiqot ishida umumiy zaxirasi 23468,7 ming tonna bo'lgan Respublikamizning quyi Amudaryo xududida joylashgan Sulton Uvays tog'-tizmasidagi Zinelbulak talk-magnezit koni tog'-jinslari asosiy ob'ekt sifatida tanlangan. Zinelbulak talk-magnezitining aniqlangan modda tarkibi bo'yicha undan amorf kremnezyomi olishning bosqichlari nazariy jihatdan yoritilgan. Unga ko'ra ushbu tog'-jinslaridan amorf kremnezuomini ajratib olish asosan Xom ashyoni dastlab 900–1200 °C haroratlarda termik qayta ishlash, ushbu namuna ishqor eritmasi bilan eritilib olingan ishqorli silikatni kislotali qayta ishlash bosqichlaridan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: *Amorf kremnezyom (SiO₂), talk, talk-magnezit, Zinelbulak talk-magnezit, rengen difraksiyalash (XRD), rengenofluorosentli taxlil (XRF), infraqizil (IQ) spektroskopiya.*

INTRODUCTION

Amorphous silica (SiO₂), due to its non-crystalline or poorly ordered crystal structure, as well as its high mechanical strength, large surface area, and chemical stability, is widely used in various industrial sectors [1]. For example, in the construction industry, it is used as an additive to cement composites to produce high-strength concrete. In addition, its large surface area and thermal stability make it a key raw material in the production of microelectronics, optical fibers, catalysts, and adsorbents[2].

In global practice, amorphous silica (SiO₂) is mainly obtained by processing various silica-containing raw materials—particularly diatomite and coal fly ash—through a series of thermal and chemical stages and processes. For instance, high-purity amorphous silica gel (with over 95% purity) can be extracted from diatomite through NaOH extraction followed by acid treatment and precipitation. The acid treatment stage is typically conducted at 60–90 °C for 4–12 hours [3]. In the case of coal fly ash, NaOH extraction is carried out at 90–100 °C, and subsequent precipitation with H₂SO₄ or CO₂ at pH ≤ 2 yields amorphous silica particles with a size of 20–40 nm and a surface area of about 115 m²/g [4].

Considering the industrial importance of amorphous silica, several practical studies have also been conducted in our country. In particular, the development of import-substituting and export-oriented directions based on the use of local raw materials, which ensure high economic efficiency, deserves special attention. It is well known that amorphous silica is mainly extracted from raw materials such as talc-magnesite, diatomite, and coal fly ash. The rocks of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite deposit, located in the Sultan Uvays mountain range in the lower Amudarya region of Uzbekistan, can serve as a primary raw material for this purpose. This ore mainly consists of talc and magnesite minerals. The total reserves of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite deposit are estimated at 23468.7 thousand tons, of which 7 738.9 thousand tons are classified under categories A+B+C₁. Currently, 1 550.8 thousand tons (20.04 %) of the talc-magnesite mineral reserves have been utilized for production. Meanwhile, 15 728.9 thousand tons of talc and talc-magnesite reserves remain unexploited and are classified under category C₂ [5; 6]. According to our previous studies, the mineral composition of this talc-magnesite raw material consists of 62 % talc and 38 % magnesite, with a specific heat capacity of 800–900 J/(kg·°C), a density of 2.8–3.0 g/cm³, and a water absorption rate of 0.3% [7].

In recent years, increased attention has been paid to the talc-magnesite rocks of this deposit. For instance, researchers in [7; 8; 9] have carried out flotation processing of Zinelbulak talc-magnesite to separate talc and a magnesite-rich pulp containing, by mass percentage: 53.70 % - magnesite, 27.20 % - talc and 9.09 % calcite and dolomite. This pulp was subsequently treated with sulfuric acid to produce fertilizers containing N-P-Mg-Ca-S and amorphous silica. Another study [5] reported the use of this raw material to produce refractory ceramic materials containing graphite.

Based on the above considerations and a review of the literature, this research focuses on identifying the chemical and mineralogical composition of Zinelbulak talc-magnesite using modern physicochemical methods, and presents preliminary results on obtaining amorphous silica from this raw material.

METHODS

The analyses were mainly conducted using X-ray phase analysis, X-ray fluorescence, infrared spectroscopy, and SEM methods. The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained using an XRD-6100 powder diffractometer controlled via computer, under CuK α radiation [10–13]. IR spectrometric analyses were performed within the infrared spectral range of 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹, with a signal-to-noise ratio of 60,000:1 and a scanning speed of 20 spectra per second [14–16].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research began with an extended analysis of the talc-magnesite ore sample using an X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Extended analysis of the talc-magnesite from Zinelbulak using X-ray fluorescence spectrometer.

Based on the analysis, the chemical composition of the raw material was determined in terms of percentage: SiO_2 - 40.80 %, MgO - 30.50 %, Fe_2O_3 - 7.12 %, Al_2O_3 - 0.94 %, CaO - 0.82 %, SO_3 - 0.05 %, MnO - 0.13 %, ZrO_2 - 0.15 %, NiO - 0.23 %, Cr_2O_3 - 0.28 %, and loss on ignition - 18.84 %.

The presence of magnesite in talc-magnesite type ores distinguishes it from other talc ores due to its high mass proportion of MgO (Figure 2).

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction pattern of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite raw material.

X-ray diffraction analysis revealed that the peak with the highest intensity at 2.74 d, Å corresponds to magnesite, while the peaks at 3.10 and 9.21 d, Å are attributed to talc. Based on the X-ray phase analysis results, the composition of the main components was determined as follows (%): talc – 55.47%, magnesite – 27.74%, chlorite – 8.01%, dolomite – 2.90%, amorphous silica – 5.5%, and calcite – 0.38%.

The sample's IR spectral analysis results were also studied. These findings confirmed the accuracy of the above X-ray fluorescence and X-ray phase analysis results (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Infrared spectroscopic analysis of talc-magnesite raw material.

In the IR spectral regions: the CO_3^{2-} ions in CaCO_3 exhibit stretching vibrations at 1541.12, 1456.26, and 999.13 cm^{-1} , and bending vibrations at 495.71 cm^{-1} ; in MgCO_3 , stretching vibrations appear at 1456.26, 1006.84, and 999.13 cm^{-1} , while bending vibrations are observed at 1716.65, 1506.41, and 746.45 cm^{-1} . In $\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot \text{CaCO}_3$, bending vibrations are observed at 1440.83 and 1446.61 cm^{-1} . For chlorite, the SiO_2 ions show stretching vibrations at 667.37 cm^{-1} and bending vibrations at 414.70 cm^{-1} . In talc, the Si–O–Si ions exhibit stretching vibrations at 2358.94 cm^{-1} and bending vibrations at 484.13 cm^{-1} . The OH^- ions present in the samples show bending vibrations at 3674.39 and 3676.32 cm^{-1} , corresponding to talc.

Based on numerous studies, it was determined that the talc-magnesite ores from the Zinelbulak deposit have a high silicon dioxide (SiO_2) content. The possibility of

obtaining amorphous silica from this raw material through processing was evaluated. According to literature sources, the following process sequence for producing amorphous silica from Zinelbulak talc-magnesite was developed (Figure 4):

1. Stage 1: The raw material is initially heated at 900–1200°C, which eliminates organic matter and activates silicon dioxide.
2. Stage 2: The heated raw material is dissolved in an alkaline solution to obtain an alkaline silicate.
3. Stage 3: The sodium silicate solution is processed with H₂SO₄ acid, and amorphous silica is precipitated and separated.
4. Stage 4: The obtained amorphous silica precipitate is filtered, washed with distilled water, and dried at 100–120°C.

Figure 4. Production steps of amorphous silica derived from Zinelbulak talc-magnesite deposit

CONCLUSION

Based on the conducted research, the chemical composition of the Zinelbulak talc-magnesite deposit was determined using modern physicochemical methods, with the following composition in percentage: SiO₂ - 37.6%, MgO - 29.10%, Fe₂O₃ - 5.90%, Al₂O₃ - 1.05%, CaO - 1.00%, SO₃ - 0.08%, MnO - 0.13%, ZrO₂ - 0.15%, NiO - 0.20%, Cr₂O₃ - 0.14%, and loss on ignition - 18.84%. Based on the results of X-ray phase analysis, the mineralogical quantitative composition of the raw material was determined relative to the main components, as follows (%): talc - 55.47%, magnesite - 27.74%, chlorite - 8.01%, dolomite - 2.90%, amorphous silica - 5.5%, and calcite - 0.38%. Based on the obtained results, the theoretical foundations for the extraction of amorphous silica from Zinelbulak talc-magnesite were developed.

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